

Clinico-Hematological Profile of Aplastic Anemia: A Cross-Sectional Study in a Referral Hospital of Eastern Odisha

Meenakshi Mohapatro¹, Phalgune Priyadarshini², Subhransu Kumar Hota³,
Siddhartha Sabyasachi⁴, Liza Das⁵, Itishree Rana⁶, Lity Mohanty⁷

¹Assistant Professor, Department of Pathology, SCB Medical College and Hospital

²Assistant Professor, Department of Pathology, SCB Medical College & Hospital

³Associate Professor, Department of Pathology, SCB Medical College and Hospital

⁴Junior Resident, Department of Pathology, SCB Medical College and Hospital

⁵Assistant Professor, Department of Pathology, SCB Medical College and Hospital

⁶Assistant Professor, Department Of Pathology, SCB Medical College and Hospital

⁷Professor and HOD, Department of Pathology, SCB Medical College and Hospital

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Corresponding Author: Dr. Meenakshi Mohapatro

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Abstract:

Introduction: Aplastic anaemia initially delineated by Paul Ehrlich in 1885, is a grievous bone marrow failure syndrome characterized by significant mortality if left untreated. Patients predominantly present with pancytopenia, evidenced by a marked decrease in hemoglobin levels (<12 g/dL), white blood cell counts (<4x10⁹/L), and platelet counts (<100x10⁹/L). The incidence of this disorder is substantially higher in Asian populations compared to Western counterparts. Etiologies encompass direct marrow insults, inherited constitutional syndromes, and immune-mediated mechanisms.

Materials and Methods: This cross-sectional study spanned four months within the Department of Pathology at SCB Medical College and Hospital, Cuttack. Diagnostic criteria included comprehensive clinical histories, physical examinations, complete blood counts (CBC), reticulocyte counts, peripheral blood smears, and bone marrow biopsy findings. Participants ranged from 12 to 65 years old, all presenting with pancytopenia. Exclusion criteria encompassed non-consenting individuals and those with cellular bone marrow or neoplastic infiltration.

Results: The cohort comprised 10 patients, with a male predominance (6 males, 60%; 4 females, 40%), yielding a male-to-female ratio of 1.5:1. The 16-30 years age group exhibited the highest incidence (40%). Clinical manifestations included breathlessness(40%), generalized weakness (30%), fever (20%), and bleeding tendencies (10%). All cases have been further sub-divided into very severe(50%),severe(40%) & non-severe cases(10%).

Discussion: The study corroborates a male predominance and heightened prevalence among younger adults. The male-to-female ratio was 1.5:1, with the peak incidence in the 16-30 years age bracket. Clinical symptoms primarily included breathlessness, generalized weakness, fever, and bleeding. The classification of aplastic anemia severity was based on complete blood counts and bone marrow study. It is categorized into non-severe, severe, and very severe types. These observations are consistent with extant literature, reinforcing the pivotal role of pancytopenia in the clinical presentation of aplastic anemia. Comparative analyses reveal congruent gender ratios and age distribution trends.

Conclusion: The clinico-hematological profile of aplastic anemia elucidates profound hematological anomalies necessitating prompt, tailored therapeutic interventions. Bone marrow examination remains indispensable for accurate diagnosis. Continuous research is imperative for the advancement of targeted therapies, enhancing patient outcomes and survival rates. The integration of innovative diagnostic methodologies and therapeutic protocols holds promise for significantly improving the quality of life for individuals afflicted with aplastic anemia.

Keywords: Aplastic Anemia, Bone Marrow Study, Cross-Sectional Study.

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Introduction

Aplastic anemia is a long standing disease first described by Paul Ehrlich in 1885(1), with clinical features detailed in the early 20th century by Cabot and other pathologists. This condition is characterized by failure of bone marrow to produce blood cells,

leading to marrow failure that, if ignored, can result in very high mortality. Most patients present with pancytopenia, which includes decreased levels of red blood cells with hemoglobin less than 12 g/dl, white blood cells with a total leucocyte count below

$4 \times 10^9/L$, and platelets below $100 \times 10^9/L$, with few subjects presenting with bicytopenia. Other causes of pancytopenia (with hypocellular marrow) could be hypoplastic MDS, severe sepsis, inherited bone marrow failure syndromes like Fanconi anemia etc.

Aplastic anemia presents with suppression of all 3 lineages leading to clinical features like fatigue, recurrent infection & easy bruising. There is absence of hepatosplenomegaly or lymphadenopathy with the exception being infection.

Underlying pathophysiology involves damage to stem cell compartment where cytotoxic T-lymphocytes release γ -interferon & TNF leading to apoptosis of stem cells [1]. Aplastic anemia may be inherited or acquired. More than 50% of cases are idiopathic.

The incidence of aplastic anemia has been rising in recent years probably because of environmental factors like increased exposure to therapeutic agents, having potential to cause depression of bone marrow, and to radioactive substances [2] Recent data suggests estimated annual incidence of 2-3 cases per million. Its incidence is more common in Asia in comparison to Europe & North America.[3]

There has been limited study on aplastic anemia from eastern India. Our study aims to evaluate clinical-hematological profile in newly diagnosed cases of aplastic anemia.

Materials & Methods

A cross-sectional study was carried out in the Department of Pathology, SCB Medical College and Hospital, Cuttack during a period of – 4 months (from January 2024 to April 2024). Approval from the Institutional Ethical Committee was obtained prior to the beginning of the study. A total of 10 cases of aplastic anemia are diagnosed in this study.

The diagnostic criteria for severe aplastic anemia (Camitta et al):

(1) Peripheral blood showing at least two out of three of the followings:

- a. Absolute reticulocyte count $<1\%$.
- b. Granulocyte count less than 500/ul.
- c. Platelet count less than 20000/ul.

(2) Bone marrow biopsy $<25\%$ of normal cellularity at that age.

The diagnostic criteria for very severe aplastic anemia

(1) Peripheral blood showing at least two out of three of the followings:

- a. Absolute reticulocyte count $<1\%$.
- b. Granulocyte count less than 200/ul.
- c. Platelet count less than 20000/ul.

(2) Bone marrow biopsy $<25\%$ of normal cellularity at that age.

The diagnostic criteria for non-severe aplastic anemia: Unable to fulfill the criteria for severe aplastic anemia with

- Granulocyte count more than 500/ul.
- Platelet count more than 20000/ul.
- Bone marrow biopsy $<30\%$ of normal cellularity with depression of 2 or more hematopoietic cell lines & absence of pancytopenia.

A detailed clinical history, physical examination, CBC including reticulocyte count, peripheral blood smear examination and bone marrow aspiration and biopsy were carried out.

Inclusion Criteria: Patients of either gender belonging to the age group of 12–65 years presenting with pancytopenia (i.e., hemoglobin <10 g/dL, total leukocyte count $<3500/cc$, and platelet count $<1,00,000/cc$) were included in the study.

Exclusion Criteria: Patients who did not give consent, patients with pancytopenia with cellular bone marrow or with neoplastic infiltration were excluded.

Bone marrow samples were collected under proper aseptic conditions in the dedicated procedure room at the department. It was conducted post administration of local anesthetic over the right posterior superior iliac spine. Biopsy samples were obtained from same site, but a little away from aspiration site. The biopsy samples were fixed in 10% neutral buffered formalin for 24 h and decalcification was done using 10% EDTA. Later paraffin blocks were embedded and slides were prepared. All peripheral blood films and bone marrow aspiration slides were stained with Leishman stain while biopsy slides were stained with hematoxylin and eosin.

Results

Table 1:

Gender	No. of Cases	percentage
Male	6	60
Female	4	40
Total	10	

During our study period, 10 cases of aplastic anemia were diagnosed. Out of 10 cases 6 participants are

male (40 %) while 4 are female (60%) showing a male preponderance [Table 1] The table 2 represents

10 cases of aplastic anemia by age group. One participant is in the <15 years group (10%). The 16-30 years age group has 4 cases (40%). One participant is in the age group of 31-50 yrs (10%). Two

participants each are seen in age group of 46-60 years & over 60 years (40%). The distribution shows a higher prevalence of aplastic anemia among younger adults aged 16-30 years.

Table 2:

Age Group	No. of Cases	percentage
0-15	1	10
16-30	4	40
31-45	1	10
46-60	2	20
>60	2	20
Total	10	100

Table 3 displays the clinical features encountered in study subjects. Breathlessness is seen in 4 study subjects (40%) while generalized weakness is seen in 3 subjects. Fever is seen in 2 subjects followed by bleeding manifestations seen in 1 subject

Table 3:

	No. of Cases	percentage
Fever	2	20
Generalized weakness	3	30
Breathlessness	4	40
Bleeding	1	10
Total	10	

Table – 4 categorizes cases into 1 Non severe cases (10%), 4 severe cases (40%) and 5 are very severe (50 %).

Table 4:

	No. of Cases	percentage
Very severe	5	50
Severe	4	40
Non-severe	1	10
Total	10	100

Figure 1: High power view: peripheral smear (pancytopenia)

Figure 2: Low power view: hypocellular marrow particle with fat spaces

Figure 3: Low power view: bone marrow biopsy showing hypocellular bone marrow with increased fat spaces

Figure 4: Low power view: Perl's Prussian blue stain showing normal iron stores (Grade-2)

Discussion

In the present study, there were 10 diagnosed cases of aplastic anemia meeting the inclusion criteria, with ages ranging from 10 years to 68 years. Among these cases, 6 were male (60%) and 4 were female (40%), indicating a higher prevalence in males with the male: female ratio being 1.5:1. Other studies showed a male preponderance as well.

As per M Mahapatra et al study [4], the median age at presentation was 25 years (range 2-83), with M:F - 2.3:1. Mean age of the patients was 27.93 +/- 18.7 years with a range of 1-80 years with the male to female ratio being 1.48:1 as per study done by Ayesha Ehsan et al [5]. As per study by Halder Biswajit et al [6], the subjects showed wide age distribution of 8-68 yrs with a sex distribution of 1.25:1. Subhajit Das

et al [7] conducted a study on a total of 22 pediatric and 20 adults among them, 29 were male and 13 were female patients, with a ratio of 2.2:1. The commonest clinical feature was that of breathlessness (80%), followed by generalized weakness (70%).

As per Das et al [7], the most common complaints among all patients was generalized weakness (71.4% cases) followed by fever (61.9% cases).

The most common clinical presentations were pallor (97%), bleeding manifestations (69.6%) and fever (54%) as per study of Mahapatra et al [4].

In the study of Bal et al [2], the commonest clinical feature was that of fever 42(66%), followed by generalized weakness 34 (54%). The classification of aplastic anemia severity is based on complete blood counts and bone marrow study. It is categorized into

non-severe (NSAA), severe (SAA), and very severe types. For patients with SAA or very severe AA, the 2-year mortality rate with only supportive care is close to 80%, with invasive fungal infections like Aspergillosis & Mucormycosis and severe bacterial sepsis being the most common causes of death. In contrast, the clinical course of NSAA is quite different; it is mostly non-life-threatening and often does not require therapy.

In the present study, very-severe cases of aplastic anemia were in maximum number (50%), followed by severe cases of aplastic anemia (40%) probably because ours is a premier referral centers.

As per study by Akhtar et al [3], among 100 patients included in this study, 56% had SAA, 24% had VSAA and 20% had NSAA. Similar findings were found in many studies [8,9]. In contrast, study by Bal et al [2] showed more of non-severe cases of aplastic anemia.

Conclusion

Aplastic anemia, a potentially life-threatening condition, can affect individuals of any age. It manifests through clinical symptoms and signs that result from the suppression of hematopoiesis, such as fever, generalized weakness, fatigue, pallor, and purpuric spots. Bone marrow examination remains a cornerstone for diagnosis, often revealing hypocellularity with a decrease in hematopoietic cells and an increase in fat cells. Managing aplastic anemia presents a significant challenge in developing countries. Our goal is to improve outcomes by enhancing awareness among patients and referring physicians, thereby minimizing the delay between diagnosis and treatment. Timely diagnosis and personalized treatment plans are vital for enhancing patient outcomes. Concurrently, continued research into the pathophysiology of aplastic anemia is critical for developing targeted therapies and improving prognosis for those affected by this potentially fatal condition. The adoption of advanced diagnostic tools and innovative treatment protocols offers the potential to

improve both the quality of life and survival rates for patients with aplastic anemia.

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